

Student Enrolment and Discipline in Public Boys' Boarding Secondary Schools in Western Region, Kenya

Enock Andanje Musambai

Educational Planning & Management, School of Education, Kibabii University, Kenya

Jane Barasa

Educational Planning & Management, School of Education, Kibabii University, Kenya

Echaune Manasi

Educational Planning & Management, School of Education, Kibabii University, Kenya

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Abstract:

School discipline is a matter of concern particularly among teachers, family, educators and other stakeholders. Students cannot learn and teachers cannot teach effectively in an undisciplined and unsafe environment and therefore order and discipline are necessary for successful educational outcomes. The purpose of the study was to investigate the influence of student enrolment on discipline in public boys' boarding secondary schools. The study was guided by B.F Skinner's theory of Reinforcement. This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The target population of the study consisted of 153 boys' boarding secondary schools. Using random sampling 74

boys boarding schools were sampled. The study sampled 314 respondents comprising of 74 deputy Principals and 240 class teachers through purposive and simple random sampling respectively. The study used a questionnaire and interview guide to gather primary data. Quantitative data was analyzed using frequencies, percentages, mean, standard deviation, Pearson correlation and linear regressions. Qualitative data was coded and reported in themes and sub-themes. The study established that student enrolment had a statistically significant influence on student discipline. The study recommended that in order to instill good discipline among students, the government should regulate student population.

Keywords: *Boys, Discipline, Enrollment, Student.*

Introduction

School population greatly contribute to the change of the prevailing school climate by modifying the school's social space and "sense of community". For instance, there exist a less frequent and direct communication between teachers, school administrators, and students in larger populated schools (Gottfredson & DiPietro, 2011). Boccardo, Schwartz, Stiefel, and Wiswall (2013) submits that students in smaller

populated schools tend to be having better interpersonal relationship as they are able to identify with the school and even with each other. Ogunyemi and Hassan (2011) argue that the issue of large school population can be counter-productive. As this makes the school to be over-congested which is an indication of the strain the student population is placing on existing educational and boarding facilities in schools. This creates sense of frustration on part

of students with the school environment seen through misconduct to voice concern.

The desire by parents to take their children to known successful schools has made some schools grow bigger in size. These schools are also favored due to their expanded and varied curriculum with adequate teaching manpower which accounts for curriculum quality. Munyasia (2008) asserts that the larger the school, the more complex the task to be accomplished, and the more complex the task of maintaining the students' discipline. This is collaborated by Stockard and Mayberry (1992) who argued that behaviour problems are so much greater in large schools that any possible virtue of larger size is cancelled out by the difficulties of maintaining an orderly learning environment. In a smaller school, it is possible for an administrator to know all the students by name as well as have a face-to-face contact with all the teachers and support staff regularly. This personal contact creates an opportunity to have a strong grip of the personnel and the whole school at large. This yields obedience which is a strong virtue of discipline.

One key feature of small schools and units is that everyone's participation is needed for clubs, teams and student government to have an adequate number of members. Rutter (1988), Stockard and Mayberry (1992) claims that staff and students generally have a stronger sense of personal efficacy in small schools and units. Students take more of the responsibility for their own learning and learning activities. The learning needs of the students, not the organizational needs of the school, drive school operations. This enhances the orderliness of a school environment (Berlon 1989, and Rutter 1988). Karagu (1982) recommended that large schools would be more effectively managed by administrators with more than 10 years' experience and higher academic qualifications. For discipline to be instilled and maintained in such schools, delegation is highly recommended by allowing teachers to participate more in the organization and administration of the school.

Okundi (2020) postulates that school size characterized by bigger population greatly

contribute to the change of the prevailing school climate by modifying the school's social space and "sense of community". He goes ahead to explain that for instance, there exist a less frequent and direct communication between teachers, school administrators and students in larger populated schools as opposed to students in smaller populated schools which tend to be having better interpersonal relationship. This is because they are able to identify with the school and even with each other. Ogunyemi and Hassan (2011) argue that the issue of large size school population can be counter-productive as this makes the school to be over-congested straining existing educational and boarding facilities in schools. This creates sense of frustration on the part of students with the school environment seen through misconduct to voice concern.

The larger the school, the more complex the task to be accomplished and the more complex the task of maintaining the students' discipline (Munyasia, 2008).

A study by Oyeniran (2014), finds that the great increase in school population in Lagos state is due to the high enrollment of students in junior secondary schools with classes carrying students between 90 - 110 or even more. Despite these good open enrolment in schools, still the inadequacies present itself through short supply of teachers, inadequate classrooms and structures in poor conditions. To the extreme, in some secondary schools the basic learning and teaching requirement like seats and desks are insufficient forcing students to sit on ransacked furniture and even on bare floor.

Large school population, tend to make schools increasingly unmanageable, leaving the teachers with the impossible task of giving individual attention to the learner's needs. The teachers' contact with the learner in school becomes so minimal to the extent that a number of poorly motivated learners can form small committees in the school to engage in non-school discussion and may result to become disorderly. Muraina and Muraina (2014) submit that such, large school population poses a serious problem to the teachers in their attempt to control and instill discipline in school, besides it could influence

how students interact with each other which may determine the level of class discipline.

According to a study conducted by, Animashaun (2009), finds that schools with small school population allows the teachers to comfortably control students' activities thereby enhancing teachers' efficiency and effectiveness in carrying out their instructional and supervisory work thereby encouraging cooperation from students. It also gives chance for the students to get personal attention from the teachers, take part fully in school activities, reduce indiscipline problems than students in schools with larger population (Muraina and Muraina ,2014)

Stockyard and Mayberry (1992) supports this in their postulation that behaviour problems are so much greater in large schools that any possible virtue of large size is cancelled out by the difficulties of maintaining an orderly learning environment. Kimani (2013) observes that in a smaller school, it is possible for an administrator to know all the students by name as well as have a face contact with all the teachers and support staff regularly. He argues that this personal contact creates an opportunity to have a strong grip of the personnel and the whole school at larger which yields obedience and discipline in general. Small schools have lower incidences of negative social behavior than do large schools. This is because students in small schools are involved in a greater variety of school activities together and that they are therefore less likely to participate in anti-social activities leading to a more conducive learning environment.

One key feature of small schools is that everyone's participation is needed for clubs, teams and student government to have an adequate number of members. As this is done, there is greater sense of belonging among students which develops patriotism to the school and hence fewer indiscipline incidences compared to larger schools. Stockyard and Mayberry (2012) argue that staff and students in small size schools tend to generally have a stronger sense of personal efficacy as students seem to take more responsibility in their learning and in learning activities. Students in these schools are driven more by their learning needs

rather than by the organizational needs of the schools. In so doing they drive the school operations hence they enhance the orderliness of the school environment. Large school population, tend to make schools increasingly, unmanageable, leaving the teachers with the impossible task of giving individual attention to the learner's needs. The teachers' contact with the learners in school becomes so minimal to the extent that a number of poorly motivated learners can form small committees in the school to engage in non-school discussion and may result to become disorderly (Okundi 2020).

Hargraves (2011) further argues that this kind of situation tends to lower students' general levels of self-esteem and also raise their degree of alienation from school. While supporting this observation Pringle (2008) observes that schools, because of their large size, that emphasize only general academic competition and place little value on students' individual needs and aspiration and other non-academic pursuits leads to disruptions and other behaviour problems among the students. Study by Animashaun (2009) found out that small sized schools with smaller population allows the teachers to comfortably control students' activities thereby enhancing teachers' efficiency and effectiveness in carrying out their instructional and supervisory work hence encouraging cooperation from students.

Muraina and Muraina (2014) supports the argument and adds that it also gives chance to the students to get personal attention from the teachers, take part fully in school activities, reduce indiscipline problems than students in school with large size. Karagu (1982) recommended that large schools would be more effectively managed by administrators with more than 10 years' experience and higher academic qualification. For discipline to be instilled and maintained in such schools, delegation is highly recommended by allowing teachers to participate more in the organization and administration of the school. From the discussion above, school size appears to have considerable impact on both students' achievements and discipline in the school.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

This study used a mixed research approach which entails collecting information by interviewing and administering questionnaires to the study population. The ex-post-facto research design was used in the study. An ex-post facto research design, according to Best and Kahn (2000), is a descriptive study in which the variables have already occurred without the researcher's influence. Using this design, the researcher looks at associations that already exist naturally and treats them by natural selection as opposed to manipulation (Oso & Onnen 2005). The design attempted to investigate the influence of schools-based factors on students' discipline in public boys' boarding secondary schools in Western Region, Kenya.

Area of Study

The study conducted in public boys' boarding secondary schools in Western region of Kenya. Western region formally Western Province is inhabited mainly by the Luhya people. After the 2013 general election, and the coming into effect of the new constitution, Western Province became the Western region, comprising four counties: Kakamega, Bungoma, Vihiga, and Busia. There are 153 public boys boarding secondary schools in Western region of Kenya. Although students' discipline is a national challenge, in Western region cases of student riots and arson have been reported in some specific schools repeatedly at times within the same term (RDE, 2022).

Study Population

According to Kohler et al., (2018) population is an entire group of individuals, events or objects having a common observation. The proposed study targeted 962 class teachers and 153 deputy Principals from 153 public boys boarding secondary schools from Western region (Bungoma-36, Kakamega-81, Busia-22 and Vihiga-14). The deputy Principals were involved in the study due to their role in managing student discipline, therefore, they were more resourceful in providing the desired information. Class teachers were chosen to participate in the study because they were regarded as custodians of student mentorship at the class level and as a link between school and home.

Sampling Procedures and Sample Size

According to Mugenda & Mugenda (2003) affirmed that for any target population less than 10,000, a sample proportion of 10-50% of the target population is a good representation. Therefore, using random sampling technique 74 public boys boarding schools were sampled for the study (20 schools per county were sampled except Vihiga County with 14 schools). Using purposive sampling technique, 74 deputy Principals' were selected to provide information on student discipline in the school. In addition, simple random sampling was used to select 240 class teachers for the purpose of the research. The summary of the sample distribution is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Sample Size of the Study

Category	Target Population (N)	Sample Size (n)	Percentage Sample (%)
Deputy Principals	153	74	48.3%
Class Teachers	962	240	25%
Total	1115	314	28.2%

Source: Researcher, 2024; Ministry of Education Office, 2024.

Table 1 shows a sample of 48.3% deputy Principals and 25% teachers. An average of 28.2% sample was adopted for this study.

Results

Descriptive Analysis of Student Enrolment in Public Boys' Boarding Secondary

The class teachers were required to assess the student enrolment in public boys' boarding secondary schools in Western Region. Their responses are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Descriptive Analysis of Student Enrolment

Statement	SA	A	U	D	SD
Its 'a challenge to handle students' misbehavior with large population	64 36.8%	47 27.0%	18 10.3%	24 13.8%	21 12.1%
Discipline problems are frequent in the school due high population	59 33.9%	65 37.4%	12 6.9%	27 15.5%	11 6.3%
It's difficult to consistently enforce rule and procedures with high student population in this school	56 32.2%	55 31.6%	18 10.3%	26 14.9%	19 10.9%
As teacher on duty, I feel my management techniques are inadequate with large student population	42 24.1%	74 42.5%	16 9.2%	24 13.8%	18 10.3%
*I usually have a challenge attending to the needs of individual students in a large class size	24 13.8%	31 17.8%	19 10.9%	55 31.6%	45 25.9%

Note: *Positive statements were changed Negative to statements for analysis

From Table 2, various aspects related to student enrolment in public boys' boarding secondary schools in Western Region were assessed. The results shows that over 60 % (strongly agreed and agreed) of class teachers indicated. It is challenge to handle students' misbehavior with large population. 64 (36.8 %) class teachers strongly agreed and 47 (27.0 %) class teachers agreed it is a challenge to handle students' misbehavior with large population. This is an indication that schools with large population face are more likely to face misbehavior from their students.

The study also establishes that over 60 % of the class teachers indicated (strongly agreed and agreed) that as teacher on duty, I feel my management techniques are inadequate with large student population. 42 (24.1 %) class teachers strongly agreed and 74 (42.5 %) class teachers agreed that as teacher on duty, they feel that their management techniques are inadequate with large student population. However, 10 (10.9%) class teachers strongly disagreed and 74 (42.5 %) class teachers disagreed that as teacher on duty, they feel that

their management techniques are inadequate with large student population.

On the contrary a majority of the class teachers class teachers disagreed (strongly disagreed and disagreed) that they usually have a challenge attending to the needs of individual students in a large class size, 45 (10.3%) class teachers strongly disagreed and 55 (31.6 %) class teachers disagreed. about one third of the class teachers (31.2 %) had challenge attending to the needs of individual students in a large class size.

Descriptive Statistics on Student Enrolment in Public Schools

On further analysis the mean index and standard deviation on the responses of the teachers on student enrolment in public boys' boarding secondary were computed. The study used the following mean scale: 1.0-1.8 = Strongly agree; 1.9-2.6 = Disagree; 2.7-3.4 = Not sure ; 3.5-4.2 = Disagree ; 4.3-5.0 = Strongly Disagree, with an average mean index was 3.0. The transformed values were later used in carrying out parametric tests. Their responses with mean values were summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics on Student Enrolment

Statement	N	Mean	Std.	Range	Std. Error of Mean
Its' a challenge to handle students' misbehavior with large population	170	2.374	.956	5	.127
Discipline problems are frequent in the school due high population	173	2.230	.861	5	.262
It's difficult to consistently enforce rule and procedures with high student population in this school	172	2.408	1.052	5	.124
As teacher on duty, I feel my management large student population is a challenge	167	2.437	.961	5	.098
*I usually have a challenge attending to the needs of individual students in a large class size	174	3.379	.568	5	.234
Composite values		2.566	.884		0.169

Note: ** Positive statement changed to negative statement for data analysis

Source: Field Data 2024

From Table 3 it can be deduced that the average mean for the study was 3.0 as derived from the minimum mean of 1.00 and the maximum mean of 5.00 respectively. Based on this finding, it was revealed that teachers agreed that students enrolment affected discipline with a mean of 2.566 and standard deviation of 0.884. This was below the average mean of 3.0.

Data from Table 3 revealed that class teachers agreed that its' a challenge to handle students' misbehavior with large population (mean = 2.374, SD= 0.956). The data from Table 3 also revealed that class teachers strongly agreed that discipline problems are frequent in the school due high population (mean = 2.230, SD= 0.861).

The class teachers agreed that it's difficult to consistently enforce rule and procedures with high student population in this school (mean = 2.408, SD= 1.052). They also agreed that as teachers on duty, management large student population is a challenge (mean = 2.437, SD= 0.961).

However, the class teachers disagreed that they usually have a challenge attending to the needs of individual students in a large class size (mean = 3.379, SD= 0.568).

Correlation Analysis between the Student Enrolment and Students' Discipline

The study further sought to investigate the relationship between student enrolment and discipline in public boys' boarding secondary schools in Western Region. To do this, a Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was computed. A correlation is a number between -1 and +1 that measures the degree of relationship between two variables. The correlation coefficient value (r) that ranges from 0.10 to 0.29 would be considered weak, from 0.30 to 0.49 would be considered medium and from 0.50 to 1.0 would be considered strong. Therefore, a positive value for the correlation would imply a positive relationship and a negative value for the correlation would imply an inverse or negative association.

All the items were appropriately reversed so that high scale represented high level of student enrolment and discipline in public boys' boarding secondary schools in Western Region. The p-value was set at .05, the null hypothesis was rejected when the p-value was less than .05 but it was accepted when the p-value obtained was greater than .05.

Preliminary analyses were performed to ensure no violation of the assumptions of normality. The study findings are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Pearson Correlation of Student Enrolment and Students' Discipline

Student enrolment and discipline (Pearson Correlation)		1	2	3	4
Students' discipline	Sig.	1			
Its 'a challenge to handle students' misbehavior with large population	Sig.	.704** .000	1		
Discipline problems are frequent in the school due high population	Sig.	.468** .024	.324** .008	1	
It's difficult to consistently enforce rule and procedures with high student population in this school	Sig.	.492** .038	.458** .037	.238 .652	1
As teacher on duty, I feel my management techniques are inadequate with large student population	Sig.	-.120 .686	.217 .759	.512** .000	.117 1.23
I usually have a challenge attending to the needs of individual students in a large class size	Sig.	.425** .000	.396** .041	.435** .019	.712** .000

Source: Author, 2023

The findings in Table 4 of the study indicate that there was statistically significant ($p < .05$) positive correlation between student enrolment and the influence on students' discipline in public boys' boarding secondary schools in Western Region. Four out of the five aspects of the student enrolment correlated with students' discipline in public boys' boarding secondary schools in Western Region. Indeed, student enrolment correlated with influence on students' discipline. The correlations were between 0.425 to 0.704. Therefore, students' discipline was likely affected by student enrolment characteristics.

The Pearson correlation index obtained on the first variable "Its 'a challenge to handle students' misbehavior with large population" was $r = 0.704$, it is strong positive correlation with $q < 0.0001$ which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$.

The second variable "discipline problems are frequent in the school due high population". ($r = 0.468$, $q = 0.024$) at $\alpha = 0.05$) moderately positively correlation with student discipline.

The third variable "It's difficult to consistently enforce rule and procedures with high student population in this school." moderately correlated with student discipline. ($r = 0.492$, $q < .038$) at $\alpha = 0.05$).

The fourth variable "I usually have a challenge attending to the needs of individual students in a large class size" moderately correlated with levels of student discipline. ($r = 0.425$, $q < 0.0001$) at $\alpha = 0.05$).

The fifth variable "As teacher on duty, I feel management of a large student population is a challenge" ($r = -0.120$, $q = 0.686$) at $\alpha = 0.05$) did not correlated with levels of student discipline.

General Correlation between Student Enrolment and Students' Discipline

To investigate whether there was any statistical relationship between the student enrolment and students' discipline, a Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was computed; with overall scores from the five aspects of students' discipline. All the items were appropriately reversed so that high scale represented high level of student enrolment and students' discipline in public boys' boarding secondary schools in Western region. The p-value was set at .05, the null hypothesis was rejected when the p-value was less than .05 but it was accepted when the p-value obtained was greater than .05. Preliminary analyses were performed to ensure no violation of the assumptions of normality. Table 5 shows the correlation analysis results.

Table 5. General Correlation between the Student Enrolment and Students' Discipline

	Pearson Correlation	Students' Discipline	Student Enrolment
students' discipline	Correlation	1	.621**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	174	174
<i>Student Enrolment</i>	Correlation	.621**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	174	174

Note:** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

The finding in Table 5 of the study shows that there was statistically significant positive correlation ($r=.621$, $n=174$, $p<0.0001$) between the student enrolment and students' discipline.

Regression Analysis of the Student Enrolment and Students' Discipline

In order to estimate the level of influence of student enrolment and students' discipline, a coefficient of determination was computed using a regression analysis whose results were as shown in Table 6.

The model was of the form: $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \epsilon$.

where

Y = Discipline in public boys' boarding secondary X_1 = Student enrolment characteristics

B_0 = Coefficient of variation ϵ_1 = the error term.

The goodness-of-fit of the model was assessed using the coefficient of determination (R^2). The results are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Goodness-of-fit Statistics

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted RSquare	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.458 ^a	.358	.315	12.5379

a. **Predictors:** (Constant), student enrolment

The results for the model summary are as presented in Table 6 where R^2 (coefficient of multiple determinants) is shown. As the model depicts, the adjusted R^2 is 0.315, an indication that there is a relationship between student enrolment and students discipline. This means that a proportion of 31.5 % of students' discipline can be explained by the student enrolment characteristics.

In assessing whether the model can significantly predict student discipline turnover in public boys boarding secondary schools, the F-statistic from the ANOVA was used. The model significance was presented using the ANOVA test. The findings were summarized in Table 7.

Table 7. ANOVA test for the Significance of the Model^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	45.2358	1	86.325	61.235	.000 ^b
Total	188.4918	374	4.2357		

a. **Dependent Variable:** students' discipline
b. **Predictors:** (Constant), student enrolment

The results in Table 7 indicated that the model was statistically significant. This was supported by an F statistic 61.235 and the reported p value (0.000) which was less than 0.05 significance

level. Therefore, at the 95 % confidence level a statistically significant influence existed between student enrolment and students' discipline, $p < 0.05$.

Table 8. Regression Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	12.32	2.324		5.3265	.000
student enrolment	.354	1.235	.312	3.2357	.000
a. Dependent Variable: students' discipline. b. Predictors: (Constant), student enrolment					

The results illustrated in Table 8 indicates that the t-test values for the student enrolment coefficient is significant at 0.05 level of significance ($t = 3.2357$, $p < 0.05$). The null hypothesis, **HO1** that,

“there is no significant influence of school enrolment on students' discipline in public boys' boarding secondary schools in Western Region”

was rejected. Implying that the student enrolment significantly influences to the overall students' discipline in public boys' boarding secondary schools in Western Region.

The findings in Table 8 echo those of Ajayi, et al.,(2017) who revealed that revealed that class size has significant influence on senior secondary students' discipline in senior secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. This finding agrees with the finding of Jacob and Olawuyi et al. (2016) who found that there is relationship between class size and discipline of secondary school students in Yagba West of Kogi State, Nigeria.

During the interview with deputy head teacher, it was established that there was a positive relationship between student enrolment and the influence on students' discipline. Respondent '9' observed that:

“There usually many discipline issues such as theft with our large student population in the school”

Similarly, respondent '21' notes :

“Training students to behave the way we want them do, especially when dealing with a large enrollment, is quite an onerous endeavor. I spent the majority of my time here even nights to assure discipline”.

In regard to student enrolment and discipline, respondent '27' remarks :

“With increased enrolment, the dormitories are very congested , this has led to vices like sexual harassment among others”

The above responses from the interviews with the deputy Principals show that the student enrolment is necessary in ensuring good discipline.

Data in Table 8 indicate the unstandardized coefficient for the variable was 0.354 and the P-value is 0.000. The new model now becomes:

$$Y = 12.32 + 0.354X_1 + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

Where $X_1 =$ student enrolment

Thus, implying that at a significance level of 0.05, student enrolment influence students' discipline by 35.4 % . The findings also indicate that the t-statistics (5.3265) is higher than the t-critical, an indication that student enrolment significantly influences students' discipline. It is evident from Table 8 that if the student

enrolment was improved by one standard deviation, then students' discipline would improve by 0.354 standard deviation units.

The study further sought to illustrate the relationship between the student enrolment and students' discipline, a scatter plot was generated as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Student Enrolment and - Students' Discipline

The scatter plot in Figure 1 shows that there was some evidence of positive correlation between the two variables (student enrolment and students' discipline), as the pattern of dots seem to slope from lower left to upper right, an indication of a positive correlation between the two variables. The line of best fit (trend line) further confirms this since the coordinate points seem to cluster near the line of best fit and are scattered around it forming almost a visible pattern. The fact that the scatters tend to

concentrate in the neighborhood of the identity line imply the relationship is real and not by chance.

Conclusion

According to the research findings, the study concludes that student enrolment significantly correlates to the overall students' discipline in public boys' boarding secondary schools.

Recommendation

In order to prevent indiscipline cases among learners, the Ministry of Education should regulate student population through expansion of secondary education in order to maintain student discipline in schools.

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